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Executive Summary

Electrochemical double layer capacitors, often called supercapacitors, are energy storage systems which accumulate and release energy through reversible ion adsorption at electrode/electrolyte interfaces. Porous carbons are commonly used as electrode materials due to their relatively low cost and good electronic conductivity. Over the past decade, most of the simulations of supercapacitors were performed at the microscopic scale, using Molecular Dynamics (MD). This allowed to understand the adsorption of ions and the effect of surface porosity on some electrochemical properties. However it is well known from experiments that commercial materials are highly inhomogeneous, while molecular simulations, where electrode sizes are a few nanometers, only allow for the inclusion of a few pores. It is therefore necessary to simulate electrodes and supercapacitors at larger scales. To this end, Lattice Porous Carbon 3D (LPC3D) is a software designed for mesoscopic simulations of capacitive properties of carbon-carbon capacitors, based on a lattice-gas model. The code calculates properties such as quantities of adsorbed ions, diffusion coefficients and Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR) spectra for ions adsorbed in porous carbons. It uses information from MD simulations as its main physical ingredient, so that the parameterization is made at the microscale.

Before the start of the MultiXscale project, LPC3D was available as an open-source serial code, written in C. It allowed to conduct simulations of ions or solvent molecules diffusing in a single carbon particle or a particle in contact with a limited amount of bulk electrolyte. Thanks to the MultiXscale project, and in particular the work reported in Deliverable 2.3 [2], LPC3D is now available as an open-source parallel code, which can be run on CPU and GPU, written using PyStencils which generates optimised C++ code. PyStencils is a companion package of the highly parallel waLBerla designed to conduct Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD). The new implementation allows to conduct simulations on several particles in contact with an electrolyte [3] and full supercapacitors, fulfilling the objective of Task 2.5 of MultiXscale.

The next step is to increase the accuracy of the model by implementing a better description of the electrolyte properties in each pore. In the initial version, quantities of ions in pores of different sizes are calculated by extrapolating data from a molecular simulation with a single pore size. This approximation becomes inaccurate for pores close to a nanometer [4]. This report describes the coupling of LPC3D with a Molecular Density Functional Theory (MDFT) code to improve the accuracy of the model. The use of MDFT rather than conventional MD to calculate the physical properties necessary to propagate the LPC3D algorithm arised from arguments linked to i) the efficiency of the method, that is much less costly from the computational point of view and ii) the accuracy of MDFT for computing free energies in the solvents of interest for supercapacitors, such as water or acetonitrile.

Figure 1: Illustration of the simulations with LPC3D and coupling with molecular simulations. To conduct a simulation on a full supercapacitor with electrodes having different pore sizes (here two electrodes are in contact with an electrolyte), it is necessary to know the electrolyte properties in each pore, e.g. the quantity of adsorbed ions. In the past, such quantities were extrapolated from a molecular simulation with a given pore size L_{MD} different from the desired pore sizes. Now, the coupling allows for calculations on multiple pore sizes, giving more accurate quantities.

1 Introduction

1.1 Scope of the deliverable

This deliverable aims at providing information on the implementation of coupling between the lattice-gas simulation code `LPC3D` and the molecular density functional theory `MDFT` code.

This report contains elements relevant to Task 3.3 - Development of a workflow for coupling molecular simulations and lattice-gas model - lead by Sorbonne Université.

1.2 Target audience

This report is intended for readers with technical expertise in High Performance Computing (HPC) or in the use of classical liquid theories to describe solvents and electrolytes. While potential users might be interested in some of the information about the underlying equations of the models, specific information about the scientific importance of the model and about how to setup calculations is better described in published works (such as 3 for `LPC3D` and 5 for `MDFT`).

1.3 Report outline

In Section 2, we briefly describe the two models and the information exchanged between them. We keep the description of `LPC3D` brief as the method was already introduced in Deliverable D2.3 [2], but more details are provided concerning `MDFT` and its main ingredients. We also discuss the work which was made in order to use `MDFT` as a Python library.

In Section 3, we describe how the coupling between `LPC3D` and `MDFT` is made. The calls to `MDFT` are either made in the initial stage for systems for which the pore size distribution is the only relevant parameter, or within the `LPC3D` main loop in more advanced cases where the calculations will depend on other parameters such as the ionic concentrations within the pores.

In Section 4, we report on the tests conducted to check the validity of the coupling and the scalability. We show that the coupled code provides similar physical results as when the `MDFT` calculations are performed externally. We show some first results on the weak and strong scalability of the approach.

Lastly, we provide some perspectives to this work. From the software engineering point of view, the main target of future months will be inter-node parallelization. In parallel we will develop new functionals for `MDFT`, that will allow for the study of complex supercapacitor systems as targeted in Task 4.2.

2 Lattice-gas and molecular simulations of electrolytes in contact with carbon

2.1 Overview of the lattice-gas model

A full description of the lattice-gas model is provided in Deliverable D2.3 [2], so that we only recall the main ingredients here. In the lattice model considered, each lattice site is either a pore or a volume of liquid for which several values need to be defined: i) a pore size (or size of the volume of liquid), ii) an energy (related to the quantities of ions or species in the site), iii) a resonant frequency (for the calculation of NMR spectra). The pore sizes are typically assigned following experimental pore size distributions [4,6–8] or pore size distributions of atomistic structures [9,10]. The site energies are usually selected following independent molecular dynamics simulations corresponding to the correct electrolyte. The resonant frequencies are extracted from Density Functional Theory (DFT) calculations [11,12]. In specific cases, all these quantities can also be assigned arbitrarily to study systematically the effects of various parameters [3,10]

Once the system is parametrized, the ion or solvent molecules motions across the lattice sites (pores in carbon particles or fluid areas) are modeled through kinetic Monte Carlo moves. The adsorbed species explore different energetic and magnetic environments throughout their motion. The trajectories of the mobile species are recorded. The diffusion coefficients, NMR spectra and other properties can be calculated from those trajectories.

As the motions of the species largely depend on the energies associated with the lattice sites and the difference between sites, the accuracy of these energies is paramount for predicting reliably electrolyte properties and electrochemical performance.

2.2 Overview of the molecular DFT model and its implementation

2.2.1 Theory and previous applications

Classical density functional theory is a classical statistical method allowing to investigate the properties of many-body systems consisting of interacting molecules, macromolecules, nanoparticles or microparticles. Similarly to the better known electronic density functional theory, it is based on an ansatz stating that for a given external potential V , there exists a unique functional Ω of the classical particle density ρ . At its minimum, which is reached for the equilibrium particle density ρ_{eq} , this functional is equal to the grand potential Ω_V [13,14], where the subscript highlights the dependence on the external potential. MDFT is a particular flavor of classical density functional theory in which the working functional is the difference between the grand potential functional and the grand potential of the homogeneous system Ω_0 , which is obtained in the absence of an external perturbation [15].

$$F[\rho] = \Omega_V[\rho] - \Omega_0 \quad (1)$$

In current works, the classical particle density represents the solvent molecules distribution. It describes the molecules as rigid entities, similarly to the most famous water models such as SPC/E or TIP4P. Thus, the knowledge of the position of the center of mass \mathbf{r} and of the absolute orientation $\mathbf{\Omega} = (\theta, \phi, \psi)$ of a molecule is sufficient to fully characterize the molecular coordinates. The molecular solvent density $\rho(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{\Omega})$ then depends on the position and orientation.

The functional is the main ingredient of MDFT. It can be extracted from a preliminary MD simulation of the pure solvent by computing the angular-dependent pair distribution function and subsequently solving the Ornstein-Zernike molecular equation using a discrete angular representation. Once an expression for the functional of equation 1 is given, its minimization gives access to both the solvent structure and the free energy of the system. In practice, this is done by discretizing the density $\rho(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{\Omega})$ on a rhombohedral spatial grid and on an angular grid. The functional is minimized by the use of a L-BFGS minimizer which requires the computation of the gradient of the functional with respect to the density. The calculation of the density for a given solute takes a few minutes, i.e. two to three orders of magnitude less than a typical MD simulation for the same system, with a comparable accuracy.

Although MDFT was originally designed to study solvation problems [5,16,17], its extension to the study of electrochemical systems such as supercapacitors has already been proven [1]. Representing a neutral pore is relatively straightforward: since the material structure is known, it is sufficient to replace the usual molecular solute by the corresponding positions and to use a conventional force field to represent the van der Waals interactions with the solvent as the external perturbation. The approach can even be extended to insulators with non-neutral local charge densities using atomic partial charges [18]. The situation is somewhat more complicated in the case of electrified carbons. Due to the application of a voltage, the local charge may fluctuate in response to the fluctuations of the adsorbed electrolyte. [19] In order to account for this effect, i.e. the polarization of electrodes under a fixed potential difference, the method proposed by Siepmann and Sprik was employed [20]: Each atom j bears a Gaussian charge

distribution of fixed width and fluctuating magnitude q_j . These charges are treated as additional degrees of freedom and are determined to ensure that the electrostatic potential V_j experienced by each carbon atom equals a prescribed value $\pm V_0$. This set of electrode charges q_j creates an electrostatic field to be added in the external potential term of the MDFT functional. [1] To obtain the equilibrium solvent density and the electrode charges it is necessary to perform successive functional minimizations and electrode charges optimizations, which increases the cost of the MDFT calculations by approximately one order of magnitude.

2.2.2 Implementation

The MDFT code is written in Modern FORTRAN program, which is partially parallelized with openMP. To ease the interfacing with LPC3D, the MDFT code was compiled with f90wrap and f2py-f90wrap to generate an mdft module that can be imported in a python script. Here is a minimal exemple of a python script allowing to perform an MDFT calculation.

```
import mdft
import numpy as np
import subprocess

#initial MDFT calc
mdft.module_init_simu.init_simu()
mdft.module_energy_minimization.energy_minimization()

eMDFT=mdft.module_energy_and_gradient.copy_ftype().tot
mdft.module_postprocessing.init_postprocessing()

print(" %f \n"%( eMDFT))
```

The `mdft.module_init_simu.init_simu()` command initiate the MDFT calculation. First, it reads the two input files, `solute.in` and `dft.in`. The `solute.in` file contains the parameters of the solute, i.e atomic coordinates and force field parameters. The `dft.in` file contains the parameters of the calculation such as box size, grid resolution, number of angles, solvent model, among others. Once the two files are read, the code computes the external potential V on each grid node using the solute and solvent parameters. The last step of this initialization process is to create the density array and to fill it with a starting value. The usual choice is to set the density to 1 everywhere except where the external potential exceeds a threshold where it is set to zero.

The `mdft.module_energy_minimization.energy_minimization()` performs the optimization. In practice it calls the different routines computing the several components of the functional in equation 1, and their gradients $\delta F[\rho]/\delta \rho(\mathbf{r}, \Omega)$ at each point (\mathbf{r}, Ω) . These gradients are passed to the minimizer which proposes a new value for the density. This process is iterated until a convergence criterium is reached. At this point, the functional has been minimized and the MDFT

Figure 2: Illustration of the use of MDFT to simulate a single electrified pore. Extracted from Reference [1]. A) Top: Comparison between MDFT and a MD simulation of the density profile for H and O atoms from water molecules. Bottom: Average solvent polarization from MDFT (left) and MD (right). The colormap represents the charge density. B) Electrostatic potential profile across the pore for different applied potentials.

computation is essentially done. One might want to extract informations out of it. For instance the command `eMDFT =mdft.module_energy_and_gradient.copy_ftype().tot` extracts the total value of the functional, i.e the solvation free energy, and

assigns it to the variable `eMDFT`. Finally, the command `mdft.module_postprocessing.init_postprocessing()` calls an MDFT subroutine which uses the equilibrium density to compute a series of observables that are stored in output files such as the radial distribution functions or the density maps displayed in figure 2.

2.3 Gaining accuracy by coupling the lattice-gas and molecular DFT approaches

In order to illustrate the interest of using MDFT within the LPC3D framework, we illustrate on Figure 2 some comparisons of the key physical properties obtained when simulating water in a single electrified carbon nanopore. The structure of the liquid, as well as its polarization, are very similar to the ones obtained using MD simulations for a fraction of the computational cost. It is possible to apply any potential difference as is done in experimental studies. In addition, whereas the calculation of the free energy of a system using MD is often cumbersome and implies the use of thermodynamic integration techniques, this quantity is a direct output from MDFT calculations. In future applications of the coupling performed in this work, MDFT will therefore be called on-the-fly by LPC3D with a different pore size and liquid composition at each step, and it will provide in return the free energies that are necessary to propagate the algorithm.

3 Implementation of the coupling between LPC3D and MDFT

To perform lattice-gas calculations, the determination of pore energies for each site is required. This is accomplished through a coupled approach between MDFT and LPC3D. The energy calculations are conducted in parallel using MDFT, and the resulting energy values are subsequently transferred to LPC3D for further processing. As most of the operations needed to conduct simulations with the lattice-gas model are stencils, the use of `PyStencils` was an obvious choice. Indeed, it allows to generate highly efficient and scalable C++ and CUDA/HIP code from the mathematical description of the model.

3.1 Workflow of LPC3D-MDFT and its initialisation

In the conventional LPC3D approach, as described in our MultiXscale Deliverable D2.3 [2], the calculations consist in an initialization, an equilibration period, a production period and finally the output of relevant quantities. The initialization mostly consists in reading the input files which contain the information on the system, such as the pore size distribution, the electrolyte species or the NMR parameters. The main ingredient, that drives the distribution of the ions between pores, is the set of site energies that are initially pre-computed using one or more molecular dynamics simulations. Due to the computational cost associated to the latter, obtaining these site energies is the main bottleneck of the approach, that limits the number and the complexity of the simulated supercapacitors.

The LPC3D-MDFT code aims at integrating this limiting step within the main calculation. The approach is based on the use of ensemble runs to leverage the use of high performance computers, and an important advantage lies in the fact that the user does not need to perform prior simulations and analyze cumbersome data from molecular dynamics. Several levels of complexity can be introduced in the calculation:

- In a first approximation, it is possible to assume that the site energies depend only on the pore size. In such a case, Figure 3 illustrates the main steps involved in conducting a calculation with LPC3D-MDFT code. Site

Figure 3: Steps involved in conducting a calculation with MDFT-LPC3D coupling code.

energies are calculated after the initialization using MDFT calculations, prior to the LPC3D loop. This phase requires the knowledge of the pore size distribution data (that cannot change during the simulation). Upon completion of the MDFT calculations, the resulting site energies are transferred to the LPC3D part. Further details on the LPC3D implementation, including its performance, are provided in Deliverable D2.3.

- It is then possible to include more variables in order to treat the problems more realistically. For example, for a given pore size the site energies can vary noticeably with the ionic concentrations. If one wants to account for the mechanical properties, this could be made by allowing the pore sizes to change dynamically upon charging. In both cases, MDFT calculations have to be involved at each step during the LPC3D loop, and the workflow now follows the diagram shown on Figure 4.

In practice this will increase by a large extent the amount of MDFT calculations, and further optimization of the code and of the functionals will be necessary as detailed in the Conclusions and perspectives section of this deliverable.

Figure 4: Steps involved in conducting a calculation with LPC3D-MDFT coupling code when the site energies vary with the ionic concentration and/or the pore sizes are allowed to change during the charging of the electrode.

3.2 Description of the MDFT-LPC3D coupling process

The integration and coupling of MDFT with LPC3D are carried out using `Pool` function, which is part of the `multi-processing` module in Python. This module provides a way to parallelize the execution of a function across multiple input values by distributing the workload among multiple processes. This is particularly useful for CPU-bound tasks, where the computation can benefit from running on multiple Central Processing Unit (CPU) cores simultaneously. This significantly enhances the performance and reduces the execution time of computationally intensive operations.

The `Pool` function is implemented as follows:

```

from multiprocessing import Pool

def init_worker():
    # Initialization code for each worker process
    pass

def process_pore_size(pore_size):
    # Function to process each pore size
    return pore_size, energy

with Pool(processes=NUM_CPU, initializer=init_worker) as pool:
    results = pool.map(process_pore_size, pore_size_distribution.keys())
  
```

In this implementation, the `Pool` function is configured with two key parameters:

- `processes`: This specifies the number of worker processes (or CPU cores) to be utilized for parallel execution. Each process operates independently, enabling concurrent task execution and maximizing computational efficiency.
- `initializer`: This optional parameter allows for the initialization of worker processes, ensuring that each process is set up with the necessary resources or configurations before task execution begins. In our code, we initialize the workers by importing MDFT (`import mdft`).

The `map` method of the `Pool` is then used to apply the `process_pore_size` function to each item in the iterable `pore_size_distribution.keys()`. This method distributes the items across the worker processes, with each process executing the function on its assigned subset of data. Once all processes complete their tasks, the results are aggregated into a single list and stored in the `results` variable.

Furthermore, the use of the `multiprocessing` module avoids the limitations of Python's Global Interpreter Lock (GIL), allowing true parallel execution across multiple CPU cores. This is especially critical for large-scale simulations or data-intensive tasks, where sequential processing would result in prohibitively long execution times.

4 Testing the validity and scalability of the coupling

4.1 Systems used for testing

To evaluate the validity and scalability of the coupling, we conducted tests on two distinct types of systems: 1) Systems with 5 different pore sizes, and 2) Systems with a realistic Pore size distribution (PSD) containing 25 pore sizes. The PSDs are shown in Figure 5 and the random distributions of pores with different sizes across the lattice are shown in Figure 6.

Figure 5: Comparison of pore size distributions for two models: a simplified "5 pore sizes" distribution and a "Realistic" one.

The performance testing specifically focused on the initialization phase of the code, which contains two main parts: The MDFT calculations and the setup and assignment of energy values to individual sites.

Figure 6: Visualization of a system with 8000 sites (20x20x20 lattice), where pore sizes are randomly distributed across the system. The left structure represents a model with 5 distinct pore sizes while the right structure illustrates a more realistic distribution with 25 to 32 pore sizes.

4.2 Validity of the implementation

To assess the validity of the newly developed LPC3D-MDFT code, its results were systematically compared with those obtained from the previous LPC3D code for the system with a realistic PSD. The comparison focused on key physical properties and numerical outputs to ensure consistency between the two implementations. The results are identical, confirming the reliability and accuracy of LPC3D-MDFT. This coherence between the two codes validates the correct-

ness of the new approach and ensures that the modifications introduced do not compromise the fundamental physics or computational robustness of the simulations.

This initial test also allows to illustrate the runtime difference between calculations with LPC3D only or with the LPC3D-MDFT coupling. Figure 7 illustrates an example of calculations realised on the CALMIP supercomputing center [21] with a lattice size of $50 \times 50 \times 50$ (125,000 sites). These results confirm that the integration of molecular level simulations in the calculations increase largely the runtime. *However, it is worth reminding here that the computational cost of the molecular simulations in LPC3D is actually hidden as independent MD simulations. Typically, these would take several days on 36-144 cores (depending on the system), that needed to be conducted in a previous stage!*

Figure 7: Runtime obtained for calculations with LPC3D and LPC3D-MDFT for systems with different pore size distributions. Calculations are done with various numbers of processes.

Figure 7 also shows that the runtime largely depends on the number of different pore sizes. Indeed, the LPC3D-MDFT code checks how many different pore sizes there are so that the number of MDFT calculations is not the number of lattice sites but the number of different pore sizes, corresponding to different energies.

4.3 Scalability

Figure 8: Illustration of the one-node speedup for the LPC3D-MDFT calculations.

The strong scaling of the LPC3D-MDFT code is illustrated on Figure 8. In that case, since the calculations were made on a node consisting of two Intel Xeon Gold 6130 16-core processors, the realistic PSD was slightly modified to include 32 pore sizes. Although we observe a deviation from ideal scaling, it is worth noting that at this stage for testing purposes we only simulated relatively small systems using MDFT. The inclusion of complex fluids, larger pores and different pore geometries as targeted in future applications will result in larger use of the CPU, from which we can expect an enhanced speedup.

5 Conclusion and perspectives

This report presents the implementation and testing of the coupling between a lattice-gas code, `LPC3D`, and a molecular DFT code, `MDFT`. The implementation was successful as it was validated and the new code provides physically meaningful results, identical to a simulation in which the two codes are used separately. To ease the interfacing, some modifications were made in the `MDFT` code in order to generate a module that can be imported within a Python script.

Although `MDFT` is a much more efficient method than the MD simulations that were previously used to parameterize the `LPC3D` calculations, its computation costs are much larger than the `PyStencils` operations that are needed to propagate the lattice dynamics in `LPC3D`. The `LPC3D-MDFT` was thus parallelized, in a first step at the node level through the use of the `multiprocessing` Python library. The strong scaling efficiency is good, considering that only small test cases have been performed so far. In real applications, better efficiency is to be expected. In the short term, the next objective is to parallelize computations across multiple nodes. To do this, it will be necessary to move away from `multiprocessing` since it does not handle inter-node communication. We will try two approaches:

- Standard MPI for communication between processes, using the `mpi4py` library.
- `Dask`, a Python library that enables parallel computations on clusters of machines. For larger calculations this would allow us to take profit from dynamic task scheduling.

We have also started a collaboration with the Energy-oriented Centre of Excellence for Exascale HPC applications (EoCoE-III) in order to port the `MDFT` code to new HPC architectures. In short, they are currently building a mini-app based on the `MDFT` main kernels using Kokkos environment. Once this is done, we will integrate it into our software. This should in principle allow us to target complex systems; for example, it would be possible to simulate complex porous geometries instead of a collection of slit pores, going one step further into realistic macroscopic systems.

The perspectives of this work are to simulate full supercapacitors, at the device scale, with an accurate microscopic description. In parallel to the software development, some work will be devoted to the derivation of adequate functionals for the systems at play. For the moment, `MDFT` is able to tackle the two solvents that are interesting in this context, water and acetonitrile. However, the description of ionic solution is in its infancy, albeit a proof-of-concept study on concentrated NaCl (1.5 mol L^{-1}) was achieved by our team (manuscript in preparation). This approach can easily be extended to other concentrations and/or other ionic species, which will be done within MultiXscale in order to simulate the systems targeted in Task 4.2 (“Demonstrating the effectiveness of the approach for the simulation of large-scale carbon electrode materials for supercapacitors”).

References

Acronyms used

HPC	High Performance Computing
CFD	Computational Fluid Dynamics
CPU	Central Processing Unit
DFT	Density Functional Theory
NMR	Nuclear Magnetic Resonance
GIL	Global Interpreter Lock
PSD	Pore size distribution
MD	Molecular Dynamics

Software mentioned

MDFT	Molecular Density Functional Theory
LPC3D	Lattice Porous Carbon 3D

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